

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part III.

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The present investigation, which is a continuation of the work of Sircar and De (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2 312) and Sircar and Pal (*ibid.*, 1932, 9, 527) was undertaken with the object of studying how the reactivity of the amino and hydroxy groups in *o*-aminophenol is influenced by the introduction of some compact heterocyclic nucleus in its molecule and also how in compounds containing two dissimilar heterocyclic rings in their molecules the properties of the different heterocyclic nuclei are affected by each other.

2-Hydroxy-3-aminophenazine (Ullmann and Mauthner, *Ber.*, 1902 35, 4305) has been chosen as the starting material and it has been found that unlike *o*-aminophenol, it is not so well adapted for the formation of heterocyclic compounds ; evidently the already existing azine ring in the molecule strongly militates against the reactivity of the *ortho*-amino and hydroxy groups. Thus the monoacetyl derivative of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine could not be made to eliminate a further molecule of water and close the ring through the free hydroxyl group. Attempts to prepare an oxazole derivative by heating the aminohydroxyphenazine either with glacial acetic acid in presence of sodium acetate or with acetic anhydride under reflux even for 10 hours, were unsuccessful. The desired oxazole formation could only be effected by heating the aminohydroxyphenazine with acetic anhydride under pressure in a sealed tube at 220-30° for about 24 hours, whilst in case of *o*-aminophenol, the oxazole formation can be effected simply by heating it with acetic anhydride for about 7 hours (Ladenburg, *Ber.*, 1876, 9, 1524). Again all attempts to prepare an oxazole by the action of benzoyl chloride on the aminohydroxyphenazine by following the method of Ladenburg (*loc. cit.*) were unsuccessful, in every case a dibenzoyl derivative being obtained. The desired oxazole could, however, be prepared in the manner described in the experimental.

2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine has also been condensed with oxalyl chloride. From an examination of the properties of the compound, thus obtained, it is found that the condensation product, instead of existing in the expected diketo form readily, tautomerises to a hydroxyketonic form.

Attempts were next made to condense the aminohydroxyphenazine with malonic and succinic acids in presence of phosphorus pentachloride according to the method indicated by Watson and Mukherjee (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 626), but the resulting products resisted all attempts for purification.

When heated in a sealed tube phthalic anhydride condenses with 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine with the loss of one molecule of water but ring-closure does not take place.

Compounds containing new heterocyclic rings have also been obtained by condensing 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine with thionyl chloride, potassium ethylxanthate and formic acid. Ring-closure with formic acid was only effected when the acid was absolutely anhydrous and even then it was necessary to heat the mixture in a sealed tube for about 40 hours at 200-30°.

Ethylene dibromide gives a closed ring compound. Though chloroacetyl chloride with *o*-aminophenol forms a closed ring compound (Aschan, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1523) with 2-hydroxy-3-aminophenazine it only attacks the amino group.

Ethyl chlorocarbonate only attacks the amino group of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine and no ring formation takes place as in the case of *o*-aminophenol (Grenvik, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1877, ii, 25, 177).

Finally 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine has been condensed with a number of aldehydes such as benzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde vanillin, salicylic aldehyde, anisic aldehyde, furfural, *o*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes and bromosalicylic aldehyde. As in the condensation of *o*-aminophenol with aldehydes, only the amino group of the hydroxyaminophenazine reacts with the aldehydes.

Many of the compounds described in the present paper, through obtained in a pure state, resisted all attempts for crystallisation due evidently to their high molecular complexity. In fact many of them are scarcely soluble in any of the organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenyl-4:5-phenazino-oxazole.—Well powdered 2:3-amino-hydroxyphenazine (1 g.) was boiled with benzoyl chloride (20 c.c.) under reflux until a clear solution was obtained. This was then concentrated when yellow needles accompanied by a black tar were obtained. These were filtered from the adhering liquid and washed free from benzoyl chloride with ether and the separated solid was crystallised from toluene (charcoal) and the yellow needles were washed with dilute caustic soda to ensure the removal of benzoic acid. After repeated crystallisation from toluene it was obtained as fine yellow needles, not melting below 300°. It is insoluble in dilute caustic soda or ammonia, readily soluble in hot toluene, glacial acetic acid and strong sulphuric acid (red coloration) and insoluble in alcohol or ether. (Found: N, 14.4. $C_{19}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 14.14 per cent).

Phenazindiketomorpholine. — 2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) was boiled with excess of oxalyl chloride (20 c.c.) for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with ether, alcohol and subsequently with dilute hydrochloric acid to remove any unchanged phenazine. It was finally washed with water and dried. On exposure the yellow crystalline powder gradually turns red. It does not melt below 300°. It is insoluble in ether, alcohol or dilute hydrochloric acid, but soluble in ammonium hydroxide, caustic soda and nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a deep red coloration. (Found: N, 16.04. $C_{14}H_7O_3N_3$ requires N, 15.85 per cent).

Thiocarboxylaminohydroxyphenazine or Thioxyphenazino-oxazole.

Thionyl chloride (10 c.c.) was added to 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.). The mixture immediately turned black and on boiling for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour under reflux, a part went into solution. This was filtered hot and the filtrate allowed to drop into water when a black microcrystalline powder was obtained which was treated with

dilute hydrochloric acid to remove any unreacted phenazine. The product was then washed with water and dried. It does not melt up to 300° . It is very sparingly soluble in water or dilute hydrochloric acid, moderately soluble in dilute alkalis, alcohol or glacial acetic acid and very soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene or aniline. It dissolves in sulphuric acid with a greenish yellow coloration which changes to red on dilution. (Found: N, 16.2. $C_{12}H_7O_2N_3S$ requires N, 16.34 per cent).

Carbonylaminohydroxyphenazine (Oxyphenazine-oxazole).

2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) was heated with excess of carbonyl chloride (in toluol solution) on a water-bath under reflux for about 2 hours. The resultant product was then filtered and washed with toluol when a black microcrystalline powder was obtained which on exposure to air turned yellow. It dissolves in most of the organic solvents, *e.g.*, alcohol, acetic acid and nitrobenzene. It is also soluble in caustic soda, ammonia and hydrochloric acid. It does not melt even at 300° . It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a red coloration. (Found: N, 18.05. $C_{13}H_6O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.79 per cent).

μ -Suphohydro-4:5-phenazino-oxazole.

An intimate mixture of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine hydrochloride (1 g.) and potassium ethylxanthate (0.7 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with alcohol (10 c.c.) at $200-230^{\circ}$ for about 10 hours. On opening the tube there was distinct smell of sulphuretted hydrogen. The separated precipitate was repeatedly washed with dilute caustic soda and water to ensure the removal of the parent substances. Finally it was purified by dissolving the substance in strong sulphuric acid and reprecipitating with the addition of water. The black mass obtained was filtered, washed with water and dried. It does not melt below 300° . It is sparingly soluble in alcohol or glacial acetic acid

and moderately so in nitrobenzene and pyridine. It is insoluble in caustic soda or ammonia and dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a bluish violet coloration. (Found: N, 16·81. $C_{13}H_7ON_3S$ requires N, 16·6 per cent).

Phenazinomorpholine.

2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0·5 g.) and ethylene dibromide (7 c.c.) were sealed together in a tube, thoroughly mixed by shaking and heated for about 12 hours at 180-200°. The product was washed with water, dilute caustic soda and finally with water and dried when a black microcrystalline powder was obtained which did not melt below 300°. It is insoluble in alcohol, ether or dilute caustic soda but soluble in acetic acid. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red coloration but is reprecipitated on the addition of water. (Found: N, 17·5. $C_{14}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 17·7 per cent).

Methylphenazino-oxazole.—Well powdered 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine (0·2 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) were heated together in a sealed tube for about 24 hours at 210-230°. The contents of the tube were diluted with water and the precipitate obtained was washed with water and treated with dilute caustic soda and subsequently with water and dried when a black microcrystalline powder was obtained which did not melt below 300°. It is insoluble in alcohol, ether, nitrobenzene or caustic soda but soluble in acetic acid. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a red coloration but is reprecipitated on addition of water.

This compound is totally different from the mono- and diacetyl compounds obtained by Ullmann and Mauthner (*loc. cit.*) in colour, solubility, m. p. as well as percentage composition of nitrogen. (Found: N, 17·4. $C_{14}H_9ON_3$ requires N, 17·8 per cent).

Phenazino-oxazole.—2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0·2 g.) and formic acid (4 c.c., 100%) were heated in a sealed tube at 280-300° for about 40 hours. The contents of the tube were washed with water, dilute caustic soda and finally with water and dried when a

black microcrystalline powder was obtained, which did not melt below 300° . It is insoluble in alcohol, ether or dilute caustic soda but soluble in acetic acid. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red coloration but is reprecipitated on the addition of water. (Found: N, 18.7. $C_{13}H_7ON_3$ requires N, 19.0 per cent).

Phthalyl 2-Amino-3-hydroxyphenazine.

An intimate mixture of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) and excess of phthalic anhydride (5 g.) was heated in a sealed tube for about 20 hours at $180-200^{\circ}$. The black mass obtained was scraped out and was repeatedly washed with warm soda and finally with water to remove the original starting materials. The black product obtained does not melt up to 300° and cannot be crystallised. It is insoluble in alcohol, ether or nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in caustic soda or ammonia but soluble in acetic acid. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red coloration but is reprecipitated on the addition of water. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{20}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 12.3 per cent).

o-Oxyphenazinourethane.—2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (1 g.) was boiled with ethyl chlorocarbonate (20 c.c.) for about 10 hours on a water-bath under reflux. The chlorocarbonic ester was distilled off and the residue washed with water and boiled. It was then dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid and the filtrate was concentrated until beautiful pale brown plates separated, m. p. $231-32^{\circ}$. It is insoluble in water, alcohol or ether but soluble in hot glacial acetic acid or nitrobenzene. It is moderately soluble in caustic soda. (Found: N, 14.5. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14.84 per cent).

Monochloroacetyl 2-amino-3-hydroxyphenazine.—2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) and chloroacetyl chloride (10 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath under reflux for about an hour and the precipitate obtained was washed with alcohol when a black powder was obtained

which turned red on exposure. It was purified several times from boiling alcohol. It dissolves in alcohol, acetic acid, nitrobenzene, caustic soda as also in hydrochloric acid. It does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 14.92. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 14.6 per cent).

* *2-Phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine.*

2:3-Aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) was boiled with benzaldehyde (15 drops) in nitrobenzene (30 c.c.) for about 1 hour when a black solution was obtained. This was filtered hot and the filtrate allowed to drop in ether, when a precipitate was obtained. This was filtered and washed repeatedly with ether and alcohol. It was then washed with caustic soda and water and finally obtained as an orange-red microcrystalline powder, not melting at 300°. It is insoluble in water, dilute ammonia, caustic soda, alcohol, glacial acetic acid, dilute hydrochloric or sulphuric acids but is moderately soluble in nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a red coloration but is reprecipitated on dilution with water. (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{19}H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 14.05 per cent).

2-(3'-Nitro)-phenylazomethine 3-hydroxyphenazine was obtained in a similar way to the preceding compound by treating 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine (1 mol.) with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 mol.). It is a dark brown powder with no tendency to crystallise or melt. It is insoluble in ether or alcohol but soluble in chloroform, nitrobenzene, pyridine or acetone but moderately soluble in caustic soda and sparingly so in ammonia. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a red coloration. (Found: N, 16.66. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3N_4$ requires N, 16.28 per cent).

* The author was not aware of the work of De and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 357) until only a few days back. These authors have prepared iminazole by the condensation of benzaldehyde with 9-amino-10-hydroxyphenanthrene. But such ring formation could be effected neither in the case of *o*-aminophenol nor in the case of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine, only the amino groups being attacked in these cases.

2-(4'-Hydroxy-5'-methoxy)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine was also prepared in a manner exactly similar to the above with 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine (0.5 g.) and vanillin (1 g.). It was obtained from glacial acetic acid as a powder which does not melt even at 300°. It is slightly soluble in dilute ammonia or alcohol, fairly soluble in caustic soda and easily soluble in glacial acetic acid. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a dark red coloration which lightens on dilution and the substance is reprecipitated. (Found: N, 12.52. $C_{20}H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires N, 12.17 per cent).

2-(2'-Hydroxy)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine was prepared by condensing 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine with salicylic aldehyde in a manner similar to the previous compound. It is yellow in colour, lacks any tendency towards crystallisation and does not melt up to 300°. It is insoluble in ether, ammonia or dilute caustic soda, sparingly soluble in alcohol and readily soluble in nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a dark red coloration which on dilution changes to red and the substance is reprecipitated. (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{19}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.33 per cent).

2-(4'-Methoxy)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine was obtained as a brown microcrystalline powder when 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine was treated with anisaldehyde as above. It does not melt even at 300° and is insoluble in alcohol and ether, but slightly soluble in caustic soda solution. It is soluble in acetic acid and nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a violet coloration which changes to yellow on dilution with water. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 12.76 per cent).

2-Furylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine was obtained as a brown precipitate with no tendency towards crystallisation from 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine and furfural. It does not melt up to 300°. It is insoluble in dilute ammonia, caustic soda or acids but sparingly soluble in alcohol or ether and considerably so in glacial acetic acid or nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a dark red coloration which changes to red on addition of water and the substance is reprecipitated. (Found: N, 14.84. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.53 per cent).

The following aldehydes also were condensed with 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine using a slightly different method: (a) *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (b) *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (c) bromosalicylaldehyde, forming *2-(2'-nitro)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine*, *2-(4'-*

nitro)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine, 2-(2'-hydroxy-5' bromo)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine respectively.

The process is to form an intimate mixture of 2:3-aminohydroxyphenazine and the aldehydes in a molecular proportion and to heat the mixture in a tube fitted with an air condenser in an oil-bath for about 7 hours at 200-210°. The product was then powdered and washed repeatedly with alcohol, ether, ammonia and finally with boiling water to dissolve out the unreacted starting materials. None of the compounds so obtained melt below 300° and they are almost similar in properties. They are purified by dissolving in boiling nitrobenzene, filtering hot, and precipitating the filtrate with ether.

2-(2'-Nitro)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine is a brownish black substance and cannot be crystallised. It is slightly soluble in alcohol and caustic soda but insoluble in ether. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a deep red coloration. On addition of water the substance is reprecipitated. (Found: N, 16.66. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3N_4$ requires N, 18.28 per cent).

2-(4'-Nitro)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine was obtained as a brown powder. A very small quantity of the substance was obtained as plates from very highly concentrated nitrobenzene solution but the yield in that case was hopelessly poor. It is insoluble in dilute ammonia, alkalis or acids but slightly soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in glacial acetic acid and exceedingly soluble in nitrobenzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a dark red coloration but is reprecipitated on dilution with water. (Found: N, 16.58. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3N_4$ requires N, 16.28 per cent).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-bromo)-phenylazomethine-3-hydroxyphenazine is a dark brown uncrystallisable powder and is slightly soluble in dilute ammonia or caustic soda. It is moderately soluble in alcohol or glacial acetic acid and fairly so in nitrobenzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a blood red coloration but is reprecipitated on addition of water. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_3Br$ requires N, 10.66 per cent).

